

USE OF DIDACTIC GAMES IN TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This article describes the methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language using didactic games, draws attention to the role of the game in the formation of the motivational sphere of education, analyzes the characteristic features of this type of training, and gives examples of classes.

Keywords: Education, didactic games, teaching methods, teacher, students, educational process, game forms

It is already long time that a linguistic principle as a basic principle of language teaching has given way to the communicative one in theory and practice. The purpose of teaching foreign students in the University is to develop their communicative competence. That is a set of programs of verbal behavior, depending on the person's ability to navigate in an environment of communication. These target principles of teaching Russian as a foreign language highlight the activity-related teaching didactic tools as an important factor for the effectiveness of the educational process. These tools include educational and, in particular, didactic games. They could not better implement a technological approach to the teaching. In the various systems of education game has special place.

Psychologists proved that game "justifies" a transition to a new language. Game is both: interesting kind of work for the student and an analogue of language exercises for the teacher, through which the skills of all kinds of speech activity are developed.

Game has a universal feature: the use of game techniques can be adapted to different goals and objectives.

Game technologies at an early stage of training provide a long-term nature of learning and mastering of skills and abilities.

An educational game is a game used in the learning process as an assignment containing the learning task (problem, problem situation), a solution of which will ensure the achievement of a specific learning goal.

Using a game in class sessions, a teacher creates and develops students' skills and ability to find necessary information, to transform it, to elaborate on its basis plans and decisions in both: stereotype and non-stereotypical situations. Recreative game elements allow students to overcome most of the difficulties associated with a conditional nature of the foreign language communication. In addition, the game situations in the classroom are designed to create an atmosphere of relaxedness and spontaneity.

Educational game should be purposeful. The unusual form of a lesson, its unconventional nature helps to maintain interest in the target language. Being introduced into the system of traditional training, educational game performs several functions: incentive-motivational, pedagogic, orienting and compensatory.

The game is used as a means of visualization and as an exercise. It is necessary to remember that game is not an end in itself, but a tool to enhance vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, reading, writing and oral expression.

Another positive feature of didactic games in the process of teaching Russian language for foreign students is a fact that preparations for a game activate students' independent work. So, it is necessary to include in it the tasks which promote self-preparation for a didactic game, and this not only to assimilate new vocabulary, but also to model certain types of speech, as well as to select needed informational materials.

With the involvement of students in the situation of a didactic game their interest to the educational activity increases dramatically, the material under study becomes more comprehensible and performance increases significantly.

Didactic game is a quite broad group of methods and techniques of organizing the educational process. The main difference between game in general and the didactic game consists of the fact that the latter has following essential features: a clearly stated purpose of learning and a corresponding teaching result. Both can be substantiated, distinguished in explicit form and are characterized by learning and cognitive orientation. A characteristic feature of such lessons is that a didactic game is included in their construction as one of the structural elements of the lesson.

Modern conceptions of educational technology are associated with the systematic and consistent practice implementation of a pre-designed, evidence-based educational process. In this sense, educational technology is a purely practical implementation of key provisions of didactics and pedagogy in general. It is already not doubted that successful teaching is impossible without technology. This is because the teaching technology is an integration of theoretical and empirical efforts to identify learning objectives, educational content, possibilities of a combination of teacher's and students' activities, necessary training forms, methods and teaching aids, as well as determination of the learning process effectiveness.

The technology also considers efficient use of time, selection of appropriate techniques, forms, procedures, individual approach, exercises appropriateness and etc. An example of the educational technology use in practice can be development and application of didactic games for teaching of a foreign language, in our case Russian language.

The main stages of preparation and conduct of DG are the following:

1. Preparatory: preparation of a teacher for a game (definition of objectives, rules and regulations of a game, training and self-preparation of students for a game, preparation of didactic, methodological and technical support of a game), evaluation of students' readiness for a game, preliminary playing groups organization.
2. Introduction to a game: introduction of a theme of a game to participants, presentation of information by teacher, tuning the students' mindset for a game, presentation of script and rules of a game, formation of playing groups, distribution of role responsibilities, giving a game task, providing didactic, methodological and technical materials.
3. Game itself: discussion of the assignment in groups, consulting of the master of a game, roles performance by participants, communicative interaction of players within the playing groups, organization of a group thinking activity (GTA) within the playing groups, discussion of solution options, choice of an optimal solution for the task, a group speaker selection, training visualization, presentation, questions and answers, intragroup discussions.

From the first days of the political independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention was paid to the implementation of radical reforms in the field of education in the country, its improvement to a higher level and raising it to the level of world education. Proof of this attention is the announcement of the basic principles of state policy in the field of education and the priority of education in the field of social development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Each social system has such concepts as education, spirituality and enlightenment, which ensure the spiritual growth of a person, which requires a comprehensive study of the changes in the science of pedagogy in connection with the development of society.

Education is a bilateral activity of teachers and students, aimed at the conscious and thorough acquisition of knowledge, skills and competencies. At the same time, the mental abilities and interests of knowledge develop, the methods of cognitive activity are mastered, a scientific worldview is being formed. The activity of the organizational form and teaching methodology is determined by the creative nature of the mental activity and thinking of students, which the teacher is guided during the lesson. The conditions of educational activity are: interaction of students and teachers through direct and feedback; independent decision making and decision making; a growing desire to acquire professional knowledge and skills; student control. It is well known that reproductive education does not produce the expected results. It's not enough for the teacher to explain the material, and the student will learn to understand, remember and apply his knowledge in practice. Today, the teacher is faced with such urgent problems as the formation of a person who is able to create novations using his creative abilities and independent thinking. I would like to quote the wise words of our ancestors: "We worship the past and strive for the future." It is known that in a rapidly developing world, the desire and demand for teaching and learning the Russian language is growing. Recently, in many foreign countries, the study of the Russian language is considered an urgent problem. Language training primarily depends on the pedagogical potential and skill of the teacher. At this time, modern teachers know a variety of methods and techniques of teaching the Russian language, and often teachers face an important choice, which method to apply to get the best result in a short period of time. Everyone knows that games develop thinking, as well as intelligence and consciousness.

The use of the game in the educational process is an unconventional teaching method, and rather refers to methods that are a pleasant addition to the lesson, however, it is becoming increasingly part of the practice of teaching a modern teacher. Such an interest in game teaching methods is very justified, as indicated by a number of specific reasons. As a teacher, I have questions such as "How to teach a future person in the age of computer science?", "How to improve the quality of students' knowledge?" I think it would be advisable to use didactic games while studying in an audience. What are didactic games? Didactic games - games that we use in the educational process as a means of language learning. The game helps the teacher to learn language and speech. The principle of communicative learning is the solution of communicative tasks by means of a non-native language. This principle is implemented in gaming activities. Below I would like to list a few game forms and tricks: 1. "Day mode" 8-10 plot or schematic pictures of the daily routine. Offer consider and then arrange in a certain sequence and explain. 2. "Alphabet in pairs" Purpose. Train letters of the alphabet and use the accusative case. Realizable material.

Russian alphabet. Description of the game. Two teams (two players) agree that the one who first pronounces the letter “M” wins. They queues pronounce one or two letters of the alphabet, but no more. Example: Player1: A Player 2: B C Player1: D Player 2: E Yo Player 1: F Player 2: I Player1: YK

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